

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIPLOMATIC SPEECH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Abstract:

This article discusses the role of diplomatic relations in the life of the state and society, as well as the ethics and methodology of speech in establishing international relations. After all, the achievement of a deep and influential character of speech in the establishment of international relations is considered an important factor contributing to the consolidation of this country on the world stage.

Key words: Diplomacy, International relations, international norms and standards, diplomatic discourse

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In the current fast-growing era, the establishment of ties between countries plays an important role in the social, economic, political, cultural and even educational growth of life. Especially, the role of the representatives of international relations in the globe has being highlighted due to the fact that this is exactly diplomats and members of diplomatic corps who establish those important bridges between countries. The achievement of a deep and influential character of speech in the establishment of international relations is considered an important factor contributing to the consolidation of this country on the world stage. From this perspective, it can be easily noticed that studying the sphere of International Relations is becoming attention-catching field of study among people of different ages. The percentage of those who give their preferences to the diplomatic study has been significantly increased for the last couple of decades.

This article discusses the observance of ethics and the assimilation of speech in establishing diplomatic relations. Diplomacy – principled activities of heads of State, government and special bodies of external relations on the implementation of the goals and objectives of the foreign policy of the state, and also to protect the rights and interests of the state abroad. [3,75] Diplomacy is the conduct of international relations through negotiation, a method, with help; and which these relations are regulated and maintained; the work or art of a diplomat; the creation of international confidence [5,156]. In this case a thorough analysis of diplomatic discourse is crucial. When speaking about diplomatic discourse, it is important to note to identify its area of usage; the circle of diplomatic communication and International Relations. Many democratic countries are gathered under one umbrella in terms of following international standards to build a democracy in their territories. Foreign policy is based on equal, mutually beneficial, partnership relations, the principles of which are regulated by national legislation (for example: norms of international law (Vienna

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convention on diplomatic relations of 1961, Convention on Privileges and Immunities of the United Nations of 1946, regulations of international meetings and conferences, other international normative acts). (4,75) Supporting the statements mentioned above, it can be said that Diplomacy is the public and official act conducted by official state members. Diplomacy is an activity carried out by peaceful means and aimed at creating international trust, strengthening and developing international relations; consequently, diplomatic discourse characterizes a set of linguistic means aimed at cooperation and achievement mutual understanding. (3,76) Every country in the universe possess their own culture, mentality and way of perception. Acting and communicating delicately is one of the key factors of successful diplomatic relations, indeed. Diplomatic speech is mainly the skill of reaching agreements during communication, putting the interests of their state first. Speaking of diplomatic speech, in turn, we can say that diplomatic speech will be goal-oriented. Taking into deep consideration above-mentioned ideas, it can be easily noted that deeper understanding of diplomatic discourse is very needed in this case.

In diplomatic discourse the addresser and addressee are the subjects in diplomatic communications and the main aim of both actors in this process is to establish international ties for the state security, cooperation, search for consent and concurrent interests with foreign countries, promoting a positive perception of the state in the world. (4,11) Without any doubt, it is trusted state representatives of each country who lead the meetings and conversations in a smooth way following the natural flow of the speech. Speaking of this type of speech kindles researches to dig deeper for better understanding and providing theoretical and practical explanations and arguments regarding fundamental elements of diplomatic speech.

Studies in the field of diplomatic discourse show that diplomatic speeches and texts consist of some structural components which help to build fragile however, meaningful units of diplomatic language. They can be divided into the following ones:

- diplomatic/political terminology
- euphemisms
- clichés
- phrases
- special signs
- abbreviations
- borrowings
- neologisms

Each of these is a crucial part of diplomatic discourse and are commonly used in official types of documents like memorandums, verbal notes and letters, and negotiations, public speeches of state leaders. Note that it is quite difficult to establish clear boundaries between separate layers of vocabulary, since there is a constant transition from one layer to another; this process is inevitably linked to the question of what context a particular word is used in. This process is inevitably connected with the question of the context in which this or that lexical unit is used lexical unit [4,102]. Each component with the diplomatic discourse is needed to be studied from semantic, pragmatic, cultural backgrounds in order to avoid misunderstandings and reach an effective and successful agreement between the diplomatic representatives of countries.

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